

WAYS TO IMPROVE THE COGNITIVE ABILITIES OF STUDENTS WITH DISABILITIES

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Annotation: The task of each teacher is to create conditions for free development, comprehensive education, active, creative future generation using pedagogical technologies in the education system. Pedagogical technologies used in the education system: game-based learning, modular learning, Training based on reference signals, computer-based learning technology, level-based learning, etc create a training, technology model of practical training, education, training, personnel, pedagogical, profession, employer requirements, professional competence.

Аннотация: Задача каждого педагога - создать условия для свободного развития, всестороннего образования, активного, творческого будущего поколения, используя педагогические технологии в системе образования. Педагогические технологии, используемые в системе образования: игровое обучение, модульное обучение, обучение на основе опорных сигналов, компьютерные технологии обучения, уровневое обучение и т.д

Ключевые слова: создат подготовка, технологии модель практического обучения, образования, подготовки.

Correction, localization, and development of deficiencies in the behavior of children with disabilities is the main goal in the system of pedagogy. In order to contribute to the overall success of the child, I sought to improve the quality of learning based on playing instruments in the development of cognitive activity of a mentally retarded child. The main factor in the development of cognitive interest of younger schoolchildren is not only the degree of their knowledge and skills, but also the need to establish an educational process, which allows you to form important mental functions of the child, ways of mental work. Cognitive activity stimulates the

need and interest in cognition of mentally retarded children, the form and content of the lesson, the ability to conduct the process of "learning" through game technologies, the art of the teacher and his emotional state. Cognitive activity is a special manifestation of a student's enthusiasm, desire for learning and knowledge. For example: in order to understand the material presented by the teacher, the student must listen carefully to him, expand and supplement the knowledge gained, read books on his own, perform such work as observation, experimentation, writing, drawing. After all, it is impossible without activity in the conscious repetition of the material covered, in learning new things, in studying its ways and skills. That is, the activity of students is necessary at all stages of the educational process.

The main conditions for the formation of cognition:

- the content of the training;
- improvement of the forms of organization of cognitive activity of students. These include: improving the effectiveness of visual aids used in the classroom, organizing cognitive games, creating interdisciplinary connections, effectively organizing students' independent work, improving feedback in learning through the rational use of various forms of knowledge verification and assessment.
- The use of effective technologies for the development of cognitive abilities of students in primary schools with developmental disabilities.
- Establish a relationship between teacher and student, student and student in the form of respect and provide warmth of heart.

The task of each teacher is to create conditions for free development, comprehensive education, active, creative future generation using pedagogical technologies in the education system. Pedagogical technologies used in the education system: game-based learning, modular learning, Training based on reference signals, computer-based learning technology, level-based learning, etc. Any learning technology requires a teacher to have deep theoretical, psychological, pedagogical methodological knowledge, pedagogical skills, deep immersion in the soul of children and the ability to comprehend it. For example, the goal of the technology of learning through play is to achieve a didactic, educational, developing,

socializing goal. At the same time, it aims to reveal the educational, cognitive and creative qualities of the child. Play is both learning and work for children. A game is a way of learning about the world around you. In addition, the game will not only teach children to overcome the difficulties they face in life, but also forms their organizational skills.

This increases the child's desire to get to know his environment with age.

In the lesson of the surrounding world, depending on the topic "seasons", you can ask the question: "where, when ? "It is possible to increase the cognitive interest of students by using the question-answer method during the lesson.

- How many months are there in a year?
- What seasons do you know? etc.

The a chapter related to the winter season, "Who is witty?" You can connect a new lesson with the previous topic before the new lesson of the game. Excerpts will be read on the topics covered. The condition is to find the name of the text, to continue, to find the features of winter. When organizing independent work of students, it is important to divide them into groups depending on the level of knowledge and conduct individual work with each of them. According to the level, students should talk about: 1st group - winter work, 2nd group - winter life of animals, 3rd group - winter games, 4th group – features of winter.

Games that are played in reading and language development lessons: "create a story by looking at a picture", "draw a picture by looking at the content of the text", etc. games are designed to introduce children to oral speech, expand their vocabulary and develop their language.

It is very important to transform the mathematics lesson in order to develop the student's cognitive ability. I made it a habit to start each lesson with "thought exercises":

- Name the fifth month of the year.
- Which color of the traffic light can you cross the road on?
- What day of the week is it today?
- Why do people need eyes?

- What number is there between 9 and 10?
- What geometric shape is the door?

Such questions immediately draw children's attention to the lesson, increase their activity and form their attention.

Thus, in improving the quality of education, it is advisable to transform methods and techniques as much as possible. Our daily search, mastering new technologies and skillfully using them in our practice is our need to provide deep and thorough education to our students

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